

LANGUAGE AND GENDER

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Abstract: Everyone knows that men and women are different in some ways. These differences can be related to the peculiarities of biology and body structure or from other dimensions. Like how to use clothes, make-up, social behavior, walking, laughing,... but the distinction between men and women is not limited to these features and the difference that seems less; But it is important, the difference is in language behavior. From linguistic research, it appears that in many societies, the speech of men and women is different. In some cases, these differences are quite compact and minor and usually no one notices them and probably them; like gestures and various facial movements, they are casual.

In fact, language expresses our identity; when we start speaking, one of the characteristics that is revealed is whether we are male or female. Men and women have different roles and functions in certain areas according to society's expectations. This, which causes differences in their social behavior, also affects their linguistic behavior.

One of the topics of interest in the interdisciplinary field of social linguistics (sociology of language) is "Language and Gender" or, more specifically, "Gender Linguistics".

Keywords: Characteristics of language, grammatical and discourse differences, feminist views of language

Introduction: Many theorists in the realm of language and gender consider language to be merely a reflection of gender, and there are differences between the language of male and female authors in grammatical areas, from the point of view of linguistic units, such as words, groups, and sentences. From the point of view of this group, men and women are not only different in terms of physical, physiological, behavior and movements; but their linguistic behavior is also different from each other. Therefore, although some consider the influence of patriarchal culture as the main reason for the emergence of a kind of masculine language in literature. And to break its dominance, they have turned to women's language and literature; but the verbal differences between men and women can be seen as arising from their social position and role in the society more than anything else. Examining the effect of

gender on language indicates that men usually elude language norms; however, women obey it. Also, men violate the grammatical rules of the language more than women, and women are more bound by the grammatical rules. Men's escape from grammar rules and women's being bound by them, although it indicates that women's minds are more systematic than men's; but this reduces the courage of women in creativity and literary innovation. The frequency of using harsh and violent words in the works of men compared to women, in addition to showing the physiological characteristics of men, can also be caused by their political-social role. The abundance of use of positive interrogative sentences in men and rhetorical questions in women can confirm that the ambiguity, complexity and mystery of women's world is more than that of men, and the frequency of use of emphatic sentences in women's works can indicate that they are ignored in social relations and necessity in social interactions.

Literature review

It is mostly believed that the background of the research about the linguistic differences between men and women does not go back from the 1970s; However, "Gary" (1998) states that even during the "Tudor" era (family ruled England from 1485 to 1603) and debates and comments about the appropriate language for women, there have been. As an example, he points to a work from 1523 AD, which under the name "On the Education of a Christian Woman" has written about appropriate language for women.

Some other researchers believe that the traces of the first researches carried out on this topic can be found in the reports of linguists who studied the native languages of different lands in the 17th century. At one time, the Europeans for the first time stepped into the Antilles (West Indian Islands) and made contact with the Caribbean indigenous; they realized that men and women speak two different languages. This was an amazing discovery that apparently had not been found anywhere else in the world. Nowhere else was the segregation of the sexes so blatant as to prompt people to declare: There really are distinct languages of men and women! In a report related to that period, it is stated as follows:

"Men have many words of their own that women understand; But they never say them. On the other hand, women have their own words and phrases that men never use; because otherwise they will be ridiculed. In this way, it seems from their conversations that women have a separate language from men." (Moeinian, 2015, p. 5)

The first academic research on the link between language and gender was carried out in 1922 by Otto Jespersen. In a chapter of his book, he examined gender differences in language. He revealed that women's language is more polite and pure, women's vocabulary is less and they show less creativity in using words!

Researches in the field of gender linguistics started in the early 1970s. In the beginning, this type of research was mostly focused on investigating the effect of gender variable on the verbal behavior of people at the phonetic level as well as the style of interaction. Sapir, Likaf, Brand, Braggin, Tradgil, Baron, Arlis, Dralik, Tannen, Mills, Gordon, Wardoff,... are among the people who have conducted research on the linguistics of gender.

In the Persian language, until now the books "Introduction to the Sociology of Language" by Yahya Madrasi and "Subordinate and Inferior in Language" by Maryam Paknahad Jabrouti and articles by Mohammad Ghanbari, Majid Dehghanizadeh, Negar Davari Ardakani, Narmin Moinian, Leila Mori, Azadeh Nemati, Sahil Farshbaf,... have been published.

Language differences between men and women

Men and women, generally have differences in terms of biology, anatomy and body structure, how to use clothes and make-up, social movements and behaviors (walking, laughing,...) and language.

linguistic research reveals that in many societies, the speech of women and men is different. In some cases, these differences are quite brief and minor, and usually no one notices them, and they probably take them casually, like gestures and various facial movements. Sometimes the distinctions between men and women are also shown in the dictionary. In some languages, this difference in vocabulary is not simply a matter of how much it is being used; Rather, they are collocation that have the same meaning; But one word is masculine and another word is feminine; For example, among the Carib islanders in the West Indies region, women use the word "koyo" for rain, and men use the word "konobu" for the same meaning.

In some languages, this difference is so great that men and women practically use different words, different pronunciations or different grammatical forms. This issue can be seen in the Japanese language, where there are different words for men and women:

Meaning	Used by male	Used by female
stomach	Hara	Anaka
eat	Kuv	Taberu
old	Boku, Ore	Watashi
mother	Ohukuro	Okasan
Tasty	Umai	Oishii

Rarely, we also come across cases where men and women speak two completely different languages; Like the Chinese language "Noshu", which was alive until recently and only women spoke it. According to reports, the last Chinese woman who spoke Noshu (the world's only language used exclusively by women!) died, and with her death, Noshu, a centuries-old written code, disappeared forever. According to the French Channel 3 television network, "Yang Yuanyi," the only woman who still

spoke Noshu, died at the age of 98 in Jianyong District, Hunan Province. According to his relatives, he was unable to read and write in Chinese. His death means extinguishing Noshu, a written language that was used centuries ago by women in some remote areas of central and southern China. Manuscripts in Noshu language are extremely few; because these writings were traditionally burned or buried with the dead. (Moinian, 2015, pp. 2-3)

Now, the language differences between men and women from two perspectives will be analyzed:

A) Grammatical differences

By studying different languages, linguists found that women use language differently than men that will be listed as following:

1- From the phonetic point of view, the linguistic difference between men and women is in the chords and pitch of the songs. Words by women are performed in supra-segmental (pressure and tone), more melodious and drawn out.

2- Women in informal conversations, frequently use gap filling “voices; like um, heh, eh,...

3- Women prefer to use words that are older, purer and more polite and closer to the standard dialect; That is, women are more bound to command language; but men violate the grammatical norms. Also, women use words in which there is some kind of sympathy and feeling. There are three reasons for women's language being more polite:

- Low social status of women
- Society's expectations from them
- Preserving dignity (Namati, nd, p. 82)

4- When speaking, women put more force and pressure on the words in order to better convey the importance of their words to the listener.

5- Women use more adjectives and adverbs of emphasis. They also use oath adverbs to emphasize their speech.

6- Women know more words related to color than men.

7- Some words, from the point of view of lexicology, have been "assigned meaning"; For example: "Hamshira (the person who has drink milk from the same mother)" which has become the characteristic of "sister" and "hamsar (spouse) " is used for "wife".

8- The spoken and colloquial language of Dari Persian is sometimes so gendered that if a man wants to insult a person, he will insult sexually female relatives (sister, mother, grandmother, etc.) the opponent. Also, this sexualization of the language includes derogatory adjectives for the wife, when a man calls his wife with the following adjectives: weak, incapable, weak, weak-willed, poor, poor, etc.

9- Languages are not affected by gender equally. In Persian and Finnish languages, there is no gender separation in the language structure. In English and Thai languages, the gender distinction is only in pronouns and nouns; But in Arabic in verb, pronoun and adjective. In French, nouns are divided according to feminine and masculine, and it is also necessary that the adjective, adjective, and pronoun used for the noun must match the gender of the noun. Another point is that in languages with grammatical gender, there is no complete agreement on what meaning is masculine and what is feminine; For example, in French, the word lune (moon) is feminine, while in German, the word mond (moon) is masculine. In the Arabic language, the moon is also masculine. (Dehghanizadeh, 1388, p. 2)

10- Men use interrogative sentences and women use emphatic sentences more.

11- In general, women and men in the society have various roles and naturally, when they are present in different roles, they use vocabulary that exists in that area. Suppose we want to ask men and women about words related to war; undoubtedly, men will provide us with more knowledge in this field; because they are more active in those roles. On the contrary, women are more dominant in the home environment or in raising children; the words they use for their children are much more than men.

b) Discourse difference:

Men and women always use language in different ways in discourse, and these differences in different usage make their languages different from each other. The most important features of men's speech are as follows:

1- The sense of seeking superiority and initiating discourse

2- Proving intellectual independence and appearing in the role of a wiser person

3- Informing (information, experience, memory,...)

4- The possibility of verbal arguments and physical encounters

5- The topic of men's discourse is related to work, politics, law, taxes, sports, etc.; But women talk more about social problems and their feelings.

6- Men's discourse is based on power, competition and criticism (ugly nicknames, threats,...); But from women it is based on equality, friendship and advice.

7- Women when speaking, observe the rights of others; For example, they respect the speaking turn, allow others to speak, and accept the speech content of others. The theme of their talks is full of cooperation and help. They can maintain close relationships with others by exchanging information and secrets. Relationships between women are not based on boss and subordinates; because accepting the role of chairmanship will disturb the equality between them. Women learn how to manage affairs without having the role of president.

8- During normal disputes, women raise their demands and objections from the crowd and do not give them a personal and individual aspect.

9- Men allow themselves to interrupt women's speech; but women do this less often. The number of women's questions in conversation is more than men's. Since asking questions has the aspect of encouraging the continuation of the conversation, and men intend to find answers by asking.

10- Among men, there are many challenges and arguments when talking. Men benefit from a better mechanism to control speech in order not to go astray. They are able to develop topics, conclude them, introduce new topics and draw conclusions. Men express their opinions clearly, while women speak more broadly and ambiguously.

Note: "Wood" identified seven characteristics of verbal communication for women: equality, support and support, maintaining communication, responsiveness, concern, tangible and cautious style. He states five characteristics for men's conversation: content-oriented, superiority-seeking, powerful and frank, individualistic and abstract, and non-responsiveness. (Intercultural communication blog)

Factors of differences

The following factors are effective and important in the emergence of language differences between men and women:

- 1- Physiological differences: vocal pitch, language learning, memory,...
- 2- Social issues: discrimination, education,...
- 3- Cultural issues: customs, manners, taboos,...
- 4- Economic issues: domination and power
- 5- Religious and sect norms
- 6- Political influence and occupation
- 7- Body and physical differences

Feminist perspectives on language

The first academic research on the link between language and gender was conducted in 1922 by Otto Jespersen. One chapter of his book examines gender differences in language. He shows that women's language is more polite and pure, women's vocabulary is less and they show less creativity in using words! "Jespersen" studies were criticized by feminists. They considered such an approach gendered and believed that it was a scientific report that supposed inferiority of women. Feminist research in this regard began in the second wave of feminism in the 1970s. Most feminists accept gender differences in language, both differences in language use and differences in language reflection; but how they report the differences with other linguists is different. Feminist research in the discussion of gender differences in language can be summarized in three perspectives (inferiority perspective, dominance perspective, and difference perspective):

- 1- The point of view of deficiency

The main representative of this view is "Robin Lakoff". In his book "Language and Status of Women", he sees the linguistic difference between men and women as evidence for the inferior position of women. By listing some differences, he concludes that women's talk is limited to superficial, non-serious issues related to their personal relationship and expressing an emotional and personal reaction to a specific issue. The speaking style of women is such that it conveys to the audience that she is insecure, hesitant and lacks confidence in what she says. According to Lakoff, these language differences do not indicate women's natural defects; Rather, it is rooted in the way society is educated. In order to eliminate the inferiority of women in language, he suggests that women gain responsibility and power by using male language strategies or neutral language, and that linguists identify language differences and the harm these differences cause. They measure, evaluate and separate the parts that can be changed.

According to Lakoff, language differences are a symptom of the disease and not its cause. According to him and his associates, language reform is basically useless and as long as the society is gendered, gendered meanings will appear again!

2-the point of view dominant

Radical feminist Dale Spender criticized Lakoff in his book *Man Made Language* in 1980. By presenting a list, he showed that he is against the linguistic differences between men and women; Because in this research, gender assumptions have closed the researcher's eyes on reality. In his opinion, in this research, language is considered as an abstract system without reference to its context. According to Spender, men have been in a position of power, dominance and control, who have been able to name the world from their own point of view and create a language that is suitable for their own purposes.

Linguistic behavior is a reflection of male authority. Men use all the power they have to dominate each other and of course women. Men always try to control the situation, specify the issues, interrupt others,... as a result, since women lack power compared to men, they use more valid language forms. , to support themselves against the stronger sex.

In all the cases that have been reviewed so far, it has been proven that considering factors; Like social class, race and age group, women consistently use faces that are closer to standard linguistic faces than the faces used by men.

One of the manifestations of the inequality of power between men and women in language is considering the male gender as the norm. Man is considered as the standard of mankind and this attitude is expressed in language in different ways.

Spender says that women have been forced to express their opinions and feelings with a language that was not made by them, such a language has placed limits on women's experience and perception. Spender emphasizes the change of

man-made semantic rules and suggests women to participate in awareness raising groups and give new positive names to their experiences. Influenced by Sapir-Whorf's theory of linguistic determinism, Spender and his associates see the use of gendered words as the reason for strengthening sexism in the society, therefore, along with reforming the society, they also try to reform the language.

3- The point of view of difference

Deborah Tannen in "You Just Don't Understand!" Accepts the verbal differences between men and women, however, she believes that it is neither caused by the inferiority of women nor the result of the all-pervading power of men. By accepting the authority of men in the society, she does not always consider this authority as the result of the intention of authority. Tannen believes that men and women have different language styles; but with the same degree of validity. In his opinion, boys and girls grow up in two different contexts that leads to difference in the styles of men and women; It is like the differences that can be seen between people from two different cultures. In the relationship between two cultures, although both cultures have the same validity; But differences may generalize misunderstandings. According to Tannen, learning the language styles of each gender by the other gender can solve many communication problems between the two genders.

Conclusion

From the study of different languages of the world, it can be seen that in different regions of the world, there is a difference between the language of women and men; These differences range from the use of two completely separate languages between men and women to differences in some vocabulary, grammatical structure, emphasis, tone of expression and the way men and women choose words. These differences can have many reasons; including historical events, the existence of opinions and beliefs; Such as taboos, the difference between the roles of men and women and the role expectations created in the process of their socialization, the requirement of rules and standards of social etiquette, especially in front of the wife's family, and the inequality of authority of women and men in society.

Women tend to interact with others in ways that maintain and increase solidarity; but men tend to interact in ways that increase their power and dignity.

We make the model of the world through philosophy, science and art; but one of the most important modeling systems is the ordinary language of everyday life. Language is the main means of information transfer in human society; but language has more capabilities than this. Language can model the world or, so to speak, pass the world through its own prism. Contrary to what they naively think, language is not just an orderly list of different passages of experience that can be cited; rather, it is also a symbolic, independent and creative organization that determines the limits and gaps of experience for us based on its formal perfection.

In this way, the bias and orientation hidden in the language, about gender differences, can specify, emphasize and strengthen these gender differences and inequalities in the real world.

In gender linguistics studies, usually to several social variables; Such as age, education, social class, job, etc. are mentioned. Of course, gender is not a static concept that remains constant and the same over time and from one society to another. This concept should be seen in a spectrum where one end is biological gender and the other end is cultural gender.

References:

1. Davari Ardakani, N.& Ayar, A. (2007). Digging into gender linguistic research. Tehran: Women's Strategic Studies Quarterly, Year 11, Number 42.
2. Dehghanizadeh, M. (2008). Language gender studies. Tehran: Howra Magazine, No. 31.
3. Ghanbari, M. (2005). Linguistics and gender. New season online magazine.
4. Hakimi, M. (2019). An introduction to general linguistics. Takhar: Ganj, first edition.
5. Madrasi, Y. (1989). An introduction to the sociology of language. Tehran: Institute of Cultural Studies and Research, first edition.
6. Moinian, N. (2015). Sociological study of language difference between women and men. Tehran: Journal of Sociological Studies, No. 33.
7. Nemati, A. (N.D.). An analysis of the linguistic differences between men and women. Tehran: Faculty of Humanities Journal, No. 5.
8. Paknahad Jabrouiti, M. (2002). Superiority and inferiority in language. Tehran: Gam Nou, first edition.
9. Yule, G. (2008). The study of language. Translated by Nasrin Heydari. Tehran: Samit, 9th edition.